

BI-STABLE PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITE LAMINATE FOR ENERGY HARVESTING

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ABSTRACT

Recently, bi-stable composite laminate is investigated for broadband energy harvesting because of its nonlinear characteristics during vibrations. This paper presents a bi-stable piezoelectric composite laminate (BPCL) for energy harvesting which consists of bi-stable hybrid symmetric laminate (BHSL) and PZT transducers bonded on the surfaces of BHSL. This bi-stable piezoelectric laminate has a better energy harvesting performance under low-frequency vibration. The open circuit voltages of the PZT transducer are predicted by finite element analysis (FEA) to illustrate the uniformity of voltage distribution, thus demonstrating the uniformity of strain distribution of PZT. Based on the assumption that the strain distributions of PZT are homogenous, a simple theoretical model is proposed to predict the output power under ideal continuous snap-through vibration pattern. This model is verified by experimental results. The maximum output power measured by experiment is 44.4 mW at 8 Hz.

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy harvesting from wasted or unused power has been a topic of discussion in recent years. Unused power exists in various forms such as industrial machines, human activity, vehicles, structures and environment sources [1]. The unused power can be converted to electrical energy by using electromagnetic, piezoelectric and electrostatic mechanisms. Compared with other alternatives, the piezoelectric transduction has some advantages such as high power density, a much simpler design and much smaller size [2]. In many cases, piezoelectric energy harvesting devices have been designed to operate close to a resonant frequency to optimize the power generation, for example, linear cantilever-type harvester [3]. However, these devices do not easily extend to applications when the excitation is unknown or random. Nonlinear devices have been considered to maximize the power harvesting capability across a broadband range of frequencies and bi-stable oscillators exhibit nonlinear characteristics during periodic inter-well vibrations [4]. Bi-stable laminates have been extensively studied for morphing or adaptive structure concepts [5, 6]. When the piezoelectric material is bonded to the surface of bi-stable laminates and the structures is repeatedly actuated between two stable configurations as a result of mechanical vibration, the large shape change has the potential to generate electrical energy by the direct piezoelectric effect [7]. Simultaneously, such harvesting devices have been shown to exhibit high levels of power generation across a wide range of frequencies.

Bi-stable unsymmetrical composite laminates with $[90_n/0_n]_T$ are recently investigated as an alternative method to achieve broadband vibration energy harvesting in a wide frequencies range, due to their complicated dynamics including nonlinear large amplitude oscillations between stable configurations [8, 9]. More than that, bi-stable composite laminates have several advantages, including design flexibility for multiple resonance tuning owing to their two-dimensional nature, and reduced complexity as no external magnets are required to achieve bi-stability [9, 10]. Arrieta *et.al* [11] introduced a cantilevered bi-stable piezoelectric composite for broadband energy harvesting and the results showed wide bands of high power. Betts *et.al* [10] proposed bi-stable composite plates with piezoelectric elements to perform broadband energy harvesting. Li *et.al* [12] presented a rectangular bi-stable piezoelectric laminate which can work around the second vibration mode.

This paper presents a bi-stable piezoelectric composite laminate (BPCL) based on bi-stable hybrid symmetric laminate (BHSL) and PZT transducer. It has two stable configurations which have the same curvatures with opposite signs. Unlike the bi-stable harvesters based on asymmetric laminate with $[0_n/90_n]_T$ which are clamped at the center point, it can be fixed at one end and works like a cantilevered harvester. It can be driven more easily. Additionally, the double curved shape and uniform deformation of BHSL are beneficial to get homogeneous and large strains for the PZT transducers. The design flexibility is enhanced due to the hybrid design. The previous work has demonstrated that the output power of BPCL outperforms the linear cantilevered harvesters [13]. Compared with the previous work, the output power of BPCL by increasing the PZTs and adjusting the stacking sequence is improved in this work. The configurations and voltages of this BPCL are investigated by FEA. Experiments were conducted to measure the output power of the PZT transducers with the standard AC-DC energy harvesting circuit. Furthermore, a simple theoretical model is proposed to predict the output power under ideal continuous snap-through vibration pattern. It can be used to roughly estimate the output power and analyze the main influence factors on output power.

2 BI-STABLE PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITE LAMINATE

The bi-stable composite laminates have attracted a lot of attention due to their ability to attain two statically stable shapes [14-16]. The bi-stability is caused by the thermal expansion mismatch between plies. When a given level of deflection is forced upon the bi-stable laminate, a sudden jump to the second stable configuration known as snap-through then occurs [17]. In this work, BHSL which is on account of the thermal expansion mismatch between the aluminum and carbon fibers is employed to form bi-stable piezoelectric composite laminate (BPCL) with PZT transducers. With layers of carbon fiber, aluminum slices, and PZTs, BPCL is designed to have two stable configurations with identical and opposite-signs curvatures. The geometry condition and stacking sequence are illustrated in Figure 1. There are two types of region, which are the hybrid region with $[90_2/Al/90_2]_T$ and the composite region with $[0/90/0_2/90/0]_T$, as shown in Figure 1(a). The PZT transducers are bonded on the composite region. In the previous work, BPCLs with this stacking sequence have higher output powers [13]. Therefore, this stacking sequence is given priority. To improve the output power, the width of the hybrid region is increased from 10 mm to 15 mm and the quantity of PZTs is increased from 20 to 32 compared to the previous work. The more detailed description of this stacking sequence is shown in Figure 2(b). One characteristic of this bi-stable laminate is that the curvatures are unevenly distributed, and the curvatures remain almost constant in the middle of the laminate. Therefore, the PZTs are arrayed in the middle of this bi-stable laminate to obtain more homogeneous and larger strains. Due to the symmetric design of stacking sequence, 16 pieces of PZT transducers are bonded symmetrically about two axes in the middle of each side of BHSL with equal transverse space to maintain the bi-stability of BPCL. The PZT transducers are arrayed on two surfaces of BHSL before curing and undergo the curing process. After the curing process, the PZT transducers are bonded firmly on BHSL. The polarization direction of the PZT transducers on both sides should be identical, to produce like charges on BHSL electrode, and the PZT transducers are connected in parallel.

Figure 1: The geometry (a) and stacking sequence (b) of BPCL.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite element model of BPCL is established using commercial finite element code ABAQUS. In FEA, the laminate is modeled using 4-node S4R shell elements, and the PZT is modeled using 8-node brick element C3D8E. The material properties of the composite laminate and PZT transducer are presented in Table 1. Tie constraint is established between the laminate and PZT. And the equation constraint should be imposed on the electrical potential degrees of the surface nodes of PZT transducers to ensure a uniform potential. The cooling process to obtain the stable configurations of BPCL includes two ‘static’ steps. The finite element model of BPCL is fixed at the center, and the electrical potential of the PZT surfaces bonded on the laminate maintains zero throughout the analysis. A small imperfection (e.g. loads or displacements) on the four corner points is employed to ensure that the analysis will move away from the unstable configuration and will converge to a stable configuration. After the first step, this imperfection can be removed in the second step. The direction of this imperfection can be changed to obtain another configuration. The detailed description of simulation for the two stable configurations is described elsewhere [13]. The temperature gradient is -100°C. The two basic stable configurations are shown in Figure 2. Due to the symmetry of configurations, the simulated open circuit voltage that is on half of the potential variations from one configuration to another one is equal to the electric potential (EPOT) at either of two configurations. The open circuit voltage of BPCL is 60.6 V.

To explain the uniformity of distribution of PZT strains, the open circuit voltages of each PZT transducers on one side of BPCL are calculated by setting up different equation constraints to ensure the uniform potential for each PZT transducers. As shown in Figure 3, the open circuit voltages of each PZT are between 65 V and 55 V, and the voltage distribution is completely symmetric about the blue dashed line. This shows that BPCL has a uniform and symmetric voltage distribution. According to piezoelectric equations, the voltage distributions can reflect the strain distributions. It means each of PZT transducers has similar strains at stable configurations. Therefore, the strain variations of each of PZT transducers are almost the same during the snap-through process, which means that all PZT transducers can be fully utilized. It is a significant characteristic of BPCL and is obviously different from the linear cantilevered harvesters.

Material	Parameter	Value	Material	Parameter	Value
CFRP	Density (kg/m ³)	$\rho=1500$	PZT	Density (kg/m ³)	$\rho=7800$
	Thickness (mm)	$t=0.125$		Thickness (mm)	$t=0.2$
	Modulus (GPa)	$E_1=125,$ $E_2=9, G_{12}=3.7$		Modulus (GPa)	$E=60.61$
	Poisson’s ratio	$\nu_{12}=0.312$		Poisson’s ratio	$\nu=0.3$
	Coefficients of thermal expansion (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	$\alpha_1=-0.1$ $\alpha_2=27$		Coefficients of thermal expansion (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	$\alpha=6.5$
Al	Density (kg/m ³)	$\rho=2500$	Piezoelectric constants (10 ⁻¹² m/V)	Piezoelectric constants (10 ⁻¹² m/V)	$d_{31}=-270$ $d_{33}=550$
	Thickness (mm)	$t=0.25$		Permittivity	$\epsilon=4100$
	Modulus (GPa)	$E=72$			
	Poisson’s ratio	$\nu=0.33$			
	Coefficients of thermal expansion (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	$\alpha=19$			

Table 1: Material properties used in finite element analysis.

Figure 2: Stable configurations of BPCL.

Figure 3: Open circuit voltage distributions of PZT transducers.

4 EXPERIMENT

BPCL was fabricated by usual autoclave techniques and the PZT transducers were bonded on BHSL by epoxy resin included in preregs during the curing process. The curing temperature was 150 °C and the curing process lasted for 3 h. When BPCL was taken out from the flat mould, the stable configurations can be observed, as predicted by FEA, as shown in Figure 4. The PZT transducers on one side with copper electrodes were connected with a copper wire. Two layers of polyimide tape were employed to sandwich the wire for protection and insulation. The other electrode was extracted from the laminate. To measure the ability of power generation, BPCL was actuated by shaker to trigger continuous snap-through vibration and generate power, as shown in Figure 5(a). A circle hole with $\Phi 5$ mm was drilled at the end of this laminate to connect to the shaker, and two clamping pieces with 65 mm \times 40 mm were employed to clamp BPCL. The dynamic responses under different frequencies and accelerations were not considered and the continuous snap-through vibration was only considered in this work. To ensure that BPCL transforms between stable configurations in each cycle, the excitation frequency used in the experiment was 8 Hz and the amplitude was 5 mm. A standard AC-DC circuit was introduced to measure the voltage output of the resistance load R , which consisted of a bridge rectifier, a filtering capacitor, and a variable resistor, as shown in Figure 5(b). To obtain the power of BPCL, the output voltages with variable load resistance were measured, and the output power P can be calculated via equation $P=V^2/R$, where V denotes the load voltage and R denotes the load resistance.

Figure 4: Experimental sample.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: (a) Power generation by shaker; (b) Classical full-wave rectifying energy harvesting circuit.

5 ANALYTICAL MODELLING AND RESULTS

In order to estimate the output power, a simple model of the output power of BPCL is developed. The PZT transducers are connected in parallel. As previous finite element analysis, the strains of each of PZT transducers are almost similar at the stable configuration of BPCL. Therefore, the strains of PZT transducers are assumed to be constant in the thickness direction. The electric displacement field of the PZT transducers corresponding to stable configurations can be represented by strains and electric field:

$$D_3 = d_{31} \frac{(\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2)}{S_{11} + S_{12}} + \varepsilon_{33} E_3 \quad (1)$$

where ε_1 and ε_2 are strains of PZT transducers in x -direction and y -direction, E_3 and D_3 are respectively the electric field and electric displacement, d_{31} is the piezoelectric coupling constant, ε_{33} denotes the electric permittivity at constant stress, S_{11} and S_{12} are elements of compliance matrix.

This model doesn't take into account the dynamic characteristics of BPCL under different vibration modes. The assumption that BPCL transforms between two stable configurations ideally is supposed. Therefore, the strain variations of PZT transducers during the continuous snap-through process are the strain differences between two stable configurations. When BPCL periodically transforms between the stable configurations, the charge generated by the PZT transducers equals to the charge goes through the load resistance in half of the cycle. Hence, using a standard AC-DC circuit, the output power of BPCL is deduced as follows:

$$\frac{V_{DC}}{R} \frac{T}{2} = \int_t^{t+\frac{T}{2}} I dt = Q_B - Q_A \quad (2)$$

$$Q_B - Q_A = A \left(\frac{d_{31} (\Delta\varepsilon_1 + \Delta\varepsilon_2)}{S_{11} + S_{12}} - 2 \frac{V_{DC}}{t} \varepsilon_{33} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$P = \frac{R \left(A d_{31} \frac{(\Delta\varepsilon_1 + \Delta\varepsilon_2)}{S_{11} + S_{12}} \right)^2}{\left(2\varepsilon_{33} A R \frac{1}{t} + \frac{T}{2} \right)^2} \quad (4)$$

where V_{DC} denotes the DC voltage applied on the load resistance, R denotes the load resistance, I denotes the output current of PZT transducers, Q_B and Q_A represents the charge in PZT transducers corresponding to stable configuration B and stable configuration A, A denotes the total area of the PZT transducers, t is the thickness of PZT transducers, T is the cycle period, $\Delta\varepsilon_1$ and $\Delta\varepsilon_2$ are strain

variations in x -direction and y -direction. When BPCL transforms between stable configurations, the FEA predicted average strain variations of PZT transducers are $\Delta\varepsilon_1=4.97\times 10^{-4}$ and $\Delta\varepsilon_2=5.51\times 10^{-4}$.

Figure 6 presents the output power of BPCL measured by experiment. The maximum output power of BPCL is 44.4 mW at 8 Hz. The calculated output powers according to equation (4) are also presented in Figure 6 for comparison. The theoretical results are in agreement with experimental results. Through theory computation, the output powers with different frequencies are compared in Figure 7. The results show that the maximum output power increases with the frequency, and the optimal resistance corresponding to the maximum output declines with frequency. With the increase of frequency, the maximum output power grows almost linearly. The maximum output power is 52.3 mW at 9 Hz, which is 3 times more than that at 3 Hz. Thus, the output power of BPCL can be improved significantly if the continuous snap-through vibration can be triggered across the high-frequency range.

Meanwhile, the strain variations and the volume of PZT transducers are other critical factors to improve the output power. The design of stacking sequence for BPCL can vary the strain variations of PZT transducers and the dynamic response of BPCL at the same time. It can be adjusted for different situations.

Figure 6: Theoretical and experimental output powers.

Figure 7: Theoretical output powers under different frequencies.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a piezoelectric composite laminate which exhibits bi-stabilities. It can output higher power and power density at a relatively lower frequency. This is owing to the characteristics of the uniform strains of PZT transducers. Meanwhile, a simple model is developed to estimate the output power roughly. The theoretical results show that improving continuous snap-through vibration frequency is an effective way to increase output power. This BPCL can be optimized by adjusting the parameters of the supporting composite structure, to adapt different situations.

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